

A VIEW ON THE LIFE AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF A. URINBOEV

Burkhanov I. M.

Senior Lecturer of FerPI Fergana, Uzbekistan

Abstract:

The article reveals A. Urinboev's contribution to the development of the history of Uzbekistan with a comparative analysis of the scientist's scientific research methods. It has been proven that the life and scientific heritage of A. Urinboev is rich.

Keywords: History, scientist, manuscript, science, student.

A. Urinboev started working at the Oriental Manuscripts Institute of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan in 1953, and until the last days of his life, i.e. until 2009, he was involved in the scientific circulation, translation, cataloging and cataloging of oriental manuscripts. .

The National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan provides the following information about A. Urinboev: From 1953 to 1960, Asomiddin Orinboev worked as a junior researcher at the institute. From 1960, he worked as a senior researcher for nine years. From 1969 to 1987, he served as the head of the department. In 1987-1993, he served as the director of the Institute of Oriental Studies. In 1993-1994, he continued his work as a department head. Information in this book may be abbreviated. Because, when examining the archive of the scientist's work, the following was found, slightly different from the above information:

- In 1953, he was a junior researcher at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the RFA;
- since December 1957, acting as a senior researcher at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the RFA;
- Since July 1961, he has been a senior researcher at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Russian Federation;
- 1961 defense of the dissertation for the candidate of historical sciences;
- From June 1969, the head of the department for the study and publication of manuscripts of the XIV-XV centuries;
- In 1970, he was awarded the medal for labor courage;

- From January 1974 to November 1987, the head of the scientific classification of Oriental manuscripts department (the name of this department was changed to "History and cataloging" in 1986);
- in 1984 he defended his dissertation to receive the title of Doctor of History;
- From November 1987 to September 1993, the director of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of UzRAS;
- 1989 "Honorary of Labor" medal and Adu Rayhon Beruni state award winner;
- 1992 awarded with the medal "Independence";
- From June 1993 to 1994, the Head of the Historiography and Cataloging Department of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Russian Federation;
- 1993 awarded with the honorary label of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 1994-1996 leading researcher of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Russian Federation;
- From September 1999 to August 2000, he was the chief researcher of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Russian Federation;
- in 1998, he was awarded the honorary label of the international "Golden Heritage" fund;
- In 2001, he was awarded the honorary title of "Honored Scientist of Uzbekistan".

A.Orinboev is married, the father of two children, and his wife, LMYepifanova, also served as a researcher at UzRFA.

From 1993 to 2009, A.Orinboev implemented projects serving the fields of history, source studies, and oriental studies as the head of local and international grants. As a result, a number of books were published as part of international scientific cooperation with historical scientists in countries such as Iran, Afghanistan, UAE, Germany, Japan and the USA.

In the books and encyclopedias that provide information about A. Orinboev's scientific activities, the scientist is recognized as a person who studies the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid era, but during the research, he also made a great contribution to the study of the history of the Kokan Khanate. it became known. This was explained in detail in the third chapter of the dissertation.

In order to obtain information about A.Urinboev's personal life, family members were contacted, and verbally collected sources are presented in the appendix of the dissertation. About the life of A. Orinboev, his brothers Salahiddin Orinboev, his daughter-in-law Saltanatxon Orinboeva, nephews Shamsiddin brother and Motabar sisters were interviewed. A.Urinboev's children live in a foreign country, so it was not possible to talk with them. From the information about his family and personal life, it can be concluded that the education of the scientist was formed at the heart of the family.

For many years, A.Urinboev taught students of subjects such as oriental studies and history in higher education institutions. He was the chairman of the State attestation exams held at the Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies. At the National University in Tashkent, he gave special course lectures on the subject of historiography and supervised master's and doctoral students[3.2.b.14.]. More than four hundred monographs, collections, scientific articles and descriptions of manuscripts were published by the scientist in different languages. This scientific heritage created by A.Urinboev was discussed in detail in the first chapter of the dissertation.

In addition, it was found that A.Urinboev also carried out large-scale scientific and organizational activities. In 1973-1988, he was the scientific secretary of the special council of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Russian Academy of Sciences, in 1988-1995, the chairman of this council,

and in 1995, he was the deputy chairman. At the same time, he worked as a member of the scientific council awarding candidate and doctorate degrees of Tashkent Islamic University (2004).

Since 1988, A.Urinboev worked as a member of the editorial board of the scientific journal "Social Sciences in Uzbekistan". Since 1990, he has been the editor-in-chief of "Sharqshunoslik" almanac magazine.

In 1996, he worked as a board member of the international Amir Temur charity fund, which was established on the occasion of the 660th anniversary of Amir Temur. The main goal of the fund is to expand the scope of research on the political, social and state administration of Amir Temur, study historical manuscript sources on the subject, publish them for introduction to the scientific community, repair historical monuments built during the era of Amir Temur and the Timurids, was to carry out activities that serve to increase the sense of patriotism among young people. Among many intellectuals of our country, A.Urinboev contributed to the development of the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid period, and to the expansion of international relations.

In A.Urinboev's work, in-depth teaching and promotion of oriental studies and history among the general public was of great importance. Along with the translation of manuscript works, he spent many years training experts in the field of scientific potential and forming them as real scientists.

In the book specially prepared for the celebration of A.Urinboev's 75th birthday, "D.Yusupova, U.Uvatov, O.Boriev, J.Djappasbaeva, Yaoi, N.Toshev, O'.Sultonov, G'.Karimov, S.G'ulomov are listed as scientists who defended and are preparing to do so under the scientific guidance of A.Urinboev [3.3.p.14].

It can be concluded that A.Urinboev's scientific heritage is on a global scale, and Uzbek history and source studies are still in the attention of the international scientific community.

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